

DEMAND AND PREFERENCES FOR THE USE OF CARDIOVASCULAR DRUGS

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Relevance: cardiovascular diseases (CVD) are the leading cause of death worldwide, including in the former Soviet Union. Not only physicians but also pharmacists play a key role in the selection and use of CVD medications, as they provide advice to patients when purchasing medications. The combination of synthetic and herbal remedies remains a relevant topic, as patients often express interest in herbal remedies as a more "natural" alternative. Studying the opinions of pharmacists and consumers allows us to identify trends in preferences and determine factors influencing therapy choices, which is important for optimizing pharmacy product offerings and improving specialist training programs.

Purpose of the study: to study trends in the use of medicinal and herbal remedies for the treatment of cardiovascular diseases in Kazakhstan, the Republic of Belarus, and the Russian Federation.

Materials and methods: the study was conducted using a questionnaire. In Kazakhstan, pharmacists from pharmacy organizations (primary pharmacists – 75.3%; pharmacy managers and their deputies – 16%) with 3 to 25 years of experience were surveyed.

In the Republic of Belarus, the survey covered pharmaceutical industry specialists: pharmacists (63.3%) and pharmacy managers/deputy managers (20%) with 13 to 25 years of experience. In the Russian Federation, the study involved visitors to pharmacies in Pyatigorsk, primarily women (66.7%) aged 60–81 with low incomes.

Results: statistical data processing revealed key trends: differences in the preferences of specialists and patients regarding the use of synthetic and herbal medications; the influence of pharmacists' professional awareness on recommendations; and the predominance of herbal remedies among certain consumer groups. Regional differences in the development of product ranges and factors in drug selection were also documented.

Conclusions: the study revealed differences in the approaches of specialists and consumers to the treatment of cardiovascular diseases. The obtained results can be used to take regional differences into account when developing pharmacy product ranges, as well as when updating pharmacist training programs, incorporating the innovative views of specialists and consumers.